

COMPARISON OF THE VISUAL ATTENTION SPAN AND PROCESSING SPEED OF CIGARETTE SMOKERS AND NON-SMOKERS USING THE TRAIL MAKING TEST AMONG YOUNG ADULTS AT THE UNIVERSITY OF CALOOCAN CITY

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ABSTRACT

The negative impacts of smoking on the body and its role in the development of different diseases have been the solid foundation of anti-smoking campaigns. However, its effects on the brain lack recognition, hence, they are not frequently highlighted. In today's society, young adults are easily influenced to start smoking. No local study has investigated the effects of cigarette smoking on the cognition of young adults. The present study aimed to investigate the effect smoking has on cognitive function of cigarette smokers and non-smokers, as to visual attention span and processing speed by utilizing the Trail Making Test A and B. The 100 subjects recruited were young adults, divided into 50 smokers and 50 non-smokers, and were instructed to complete the test in under 10 minutes. The study found that the majority of smokers were male who have been smoking for 5-6 years, with an average consumption of more than 23 sticks per day. It also showed that smoking may have an effect on rote memory as seen in TMT-A scores. Overall, there is sufficient data to conclude cigarette smoking has a significant effect on visual attention span and processing speed. A noteworthy association was also observed on gender, indicating that men had a slower time executing the test. However, this study does not clearly show that smoking cigarettes has a significant impact on their performance in comparison to women, as there may be additional factors aside from smoking. With these findings, encouragement and campaign to the general public on the importance

of quitting smoking is refocused, and further research on the effect of smoking on other cognitive functions is needed to better understand its full effects on the brain.

Keywords: *cigarettes, smoking, cognitive function, health, Trail Making Test*

INTRODUCTION

The tobacco epidemic is a major global public health problem. Despite aggressive antismoking strategies, the prevalence of tobacco smoking continues to rise. In the Philippines, one in five, or 15.1 million Filipinos ages 15 years and older, are current tobacco users (WHO, 2021).

Smoking has adverse health effects on nearly every organ of the body. Its role in the development of cancer, cardiovascular diseases, stroke, diabetes, and chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases are well-established. In the last decade, studies have investigated the effects of smoking on cognitive function. However, this has not been highlighted in information campaigns.

Nicotine in cigarettes has a function similar to that of acetylcholine, which is a neurotransmitter found in the brain, modulating cognition (Bashir, 2017). Because of the similarity in function, it has an effect on receptors which support daily cognitive tasks, including memory, attention, decision-making, and reward systems. However, nicotine can also be detrimental to cognitive functions. Heavy smoking is associated with cognitive impairment and cognitive decline in middle (Campos, 2016). In a study of 73 smokers and 84 group-matched non-smokers, the performance of smokers was poorer on almost all neuropsychiatric domains (selective attention, alternating attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, processing accuracy, and executive function) except for processing speed (Nadar, 2021). Furthermore, Rios (2021) found that heavy smoking had worse performance than light smoking on cognitive functions, visual search and attention tests, and letter-number sequencing tests. In both studies, the subjects were adults aged more than 45 years.

Among young adults, Vajravelu (2015) noted decreased cognitive performances in 30 mild smokers, 30 moderate smokers, and 30 heavy smokers compared to 30 nonsmokers in India. Contrast, Pandey (2017) found no association between smoking and cognition among 23 smokers and 23 non-smokers.

A review of the literature showed no local study on the effects of cigarette smoking on the cognitive functions of young adults. This study aims to compare the cognitive functions of cigarette smokers and non-smokers among young Filipinos. The results, whether a correlation is seen or not, will make them aware that cigarette smoking can affect cognitive function and quit the habit.

Research Questions

1. Describe the demographic profile of young Filipino adults at the University of Caloocan City - Camarin as to:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Sex
 - 1.3. Year level
 - 1.4. History of smoking
 - 1.5. Number of years as smoker
 - 1.6. Average number of sticks of cigarettes consumed per day
2. Determine the cognitive function of young Filipino adults at the University of Caloocan City - Camarin using the Trail Making Test (TMT) as to:
 - 2.1. Visual attention span
 - 2.2. Processing speed
3. Compare the TMT results of cigarette smokers and non-smokers among young Filipino adults at the University of Caloocan City - Camarin
4. Determine the association between the demographic characteristics of cigarette smokers and non-smokers and their TMT results

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at the University of Caloocan City - Camarin Campus, where students from the College of Criminology attended face-to-face classes. Purposive and convenience sampling methods, both non-probability approaches, were used to select 100 undergraduate students, consisting of 50 smokers and 50 non-smokers, aged 18 to 25.

Participants were chosen based on specific criteria: they had to be currently enrolled students aged 18-25, with smokers being exclusive cigarette users and non-smokers having no history of smoking nor vaping. The data gathering procedure was approved by the School of Respiratory Therapy Research Committee, the Dean of the College of Criminology at the University of Caloocan, and the Data Privacy Office in which informed consents were obtained from all participants before the test was administered face-to-face.

The researchers administered the Trail Making Test (TMT), which measured cognitive functions such as visual attention, processing speed, working memory, and executive functioning (Bowie, 2006). The test had two parts: Part A involved connecting numbered circles in ascending order, while Part B required alternating between both numbers and letters in an ascending order. Scores were based on completion time, including corrections, and each test took 5-10 minutes to complete. If the participant is unable to finish the test in five (5) minutes, the test is discontinued. The average time to complete each test will be determined. The average time to complete TMT-A is 29

seconds and 75 seconds for TMT-B. A deficient score for TMT-A is greater than 78 seconds and more than 273 seconds for TMT-B.

Data analysis was conducted using Microsoft Excel and Jamovi, with demographic characteristics analyzed through frequencies and percentages and the means of the time taken to complete the test will be computed. The t-test was used to compare the means of the test completion times between smokers and non-smokers. The Pearson correlation test was used to assess associations between the demographic characteristics and the mean test scores of the two groups.

The study focuses on the cognitive functions of visual attention span and processing speed among traditional cigarette smokers and non-smokers aged 18-25 from the College of Criminology at the University of Caloocan City - Camarin Campus. It is specifically limited to the effects of traditional cigarette use, excluding other tobacco products or devices from consideration. While the Trail Making Test (TMT) is a reliable tool for assessing certain cognitive functions, it may not capture all cognitive functions affected by smoking, suggesting the need for further studies.

RESULTS

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of 100 undergraduate students of the College of Criminology at the University of Caloocan City - Camarin.

Characteristic	n (%)
Age (in years)	
18	29
19	18
20	16
21	12
22	16
23	5
24	2
25	2
Sex	
Male	59

Female		41
Year Level		
	1st	43
	2nd	10
3rd		22
4th		25
Smoking History		
Yes		50
No		50
Number of Years Smoking		
0		50
<1		4
1-2		14
3-4		11
5-6		20
7-8		1
Average Number of Sticks Consumed Daily		
0		50
<5		6
5-10		20
11-15		1
>15		23

Table 2. Summary of University of Caloocan City - Camarin students' TMT-A scores (in seconds) between Smokers and Non-Smokers (n=100).

TMT-A Scores	n(%)		Mean ± SD		Median (min.-max.)	
	Smokers	Non-Smokers	Smokers	Non-Smokers	Smokers	Non-Smokers
UC students TMT-A Scores	50	50	35.4 ± 14.7	31.3 ± 10.1	32.8 (17.5-99.3)	28.3 (14.0-60.0)
Average	49	50	34.1 ± 11.6	31.3 ± 10.1	32.8 (17.5-68.8)	28.3 (14.0-60.0)
Deficient	1	0	99.3 ± NA	NA	99.3 (99.3-99.3)	NA

Table 3. Summary of University of Caloocan City - Camarin students' TMT-B scores (in seconds) between Smokers and Non-Smokers (n=100)

TMT-B Scores	n(%)		Mean ± SD		Median (min.-max.)	
	Smokers	Non-Smokers	Smokers	Non-Smokers	Smokers	Non-Smokers
UC students TMT-B Scores	50	50	65.6 ± 21.4	65.7 ± 22.26	61.0 (36.2129.7)	61.2 (34.0124)
Average	50	50	65.6 ± 21.4	65.7 ± 22.26	61.0 (36.2129.7)	61.2 (34.0124)
Deficient	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table 4. Differences in TMT-A and TMT-B scores (in seconds) between Smokers and Non-Smokers of University of Caloocan City - Camarin Students.

	Test statistic	p-value	Mean Difference
TMT-A score	1.64	0.052	4.15
TMT-B Score	-0.0322	0.513	-0.142

Table 5. . Correlation coefficients of the TMT-A and TMT-B scores (in seconds) with sociodemographic characteristics of young Filipino adults at the University of Caloocan City - Camarin.

Sociodemographic Characteristics	TMT-A scores		TMT-B scores	
	Test statistic	P-value	Test statistic	P-value
Age	0.022	0.83	0.027	0.792
Sex	0.125	0.217	0.257	0.01*
Year Level	0.109	0.279	0.032	0.752
Smoking History	0.155	0.123	-0.003	0.974
Number of Years Smoking	0.141	0.162	-0.042	0.679
Average Number of Sticks Consumed per day	0.026	0.801	-0.031	0.759

NOTE: * = $p < 0.05$

DISCUSSION

1. From the 100 responses of the students at the University of Caloocan City Camarin, the distribution of demographic characteristics of the respondents is presented in Table 1. The majority of students who participated in the study were 18 years old (39%), predominantly male (63%), and enrolled in the first year (43%). There were 50 students in both the smoker and non-smoker groups. Among smokers, the majority had been smoking for 5-6 years, with an average consumption of more than 15 sticks per day.

2. Table 2 below presents the summary of TMT-A scores (in seconds) between smokers and non-smokers students at the University of Caloocan City - Camarin. Within the smoking group, scores range from 17.5 seconds to 99.3 seconds, with one student obtaining a Deficient score. In contrast, the non-smoking group exhibits scores ranging from 14 to 60 seconds. The results highlight that, on average, the non-smoker group achieved a lower TMT-A score than the smoker group, suggesting a faster completion time for the TMT-A although not statistically significant (refer to Table 4).

Nadar's (2021) study revealed a significant relationship between smoking and cognitive performance. Chronic smokers showed poorer performance in visual attention but exhibited similar processing speed to non-smokers. Lower alternating attention in smokers demonstrates the difficulty of being able to shift and refocus their attention in response to environmental stimuli. In contrast, smokers in Gulcan's (2018) study exhibit a poorer processing speed than non-smokers. It is sensible to assume that smoking may impair processing speed as a result of poorer visual attention performance. Consistent with the study, Vajravelu (2015) states that the cognitive performance of smokers is significantly decreased than non-smokers.

3. Similarly, Table 3 presents a summary of TMT-B scores (in seconds) for both smokers and non-smokers. The TMT-B scores range from 34 to 129.7, and no student within either group received a Deficient score. The mean scores reveal a marginal difference between the two groups, with the non-smoker group exhibiting a slightly higher mean score, approximately 0.1 greater than the smoker group. However, the difference in the means and the minimum and maximum values (in seconds) between the two groups is not statistically significant.

The findings in the table are in contrast with Gülcan's (2018) findings, where the current smokers' TMT-B scores were significantly higher than non-smokers. However, these results are consistent with Nadar's (2021) study, where smokers showed a processing speed equivalent to the non-smokers although they are reported to have made more mistakes, affecting their processing speed.

4. As shown in Table 4, the independent samples' t-test exhibits that there is sufficient evidence to say that the TMT-A scores of the University of Caloocan City Camarin Criminology students are significantly higher in the smoker group than in the non-smoker group. This is evident from the generated p-value that is less than or equal to 0.05. On the other hand, there is no sufficient evidence to say that the TMTB scores of the smoker group is higher than the non-smoker group, as seen from the p-value greater than 0.05. Furthermore, the observed mean difference in TMT-B scores between the two groups were found to be very small, indicating minimal practical significance. Overall, there is a significant difference in the TMT-A scores and no significant difference in the TMT-B scores, suggesting that smoking may affect rote memory which heavily relies on routine and repetition (Ciolek, 2020).

This outcome is in contrast with Pandey's (2017) cross-sectional study conducted among healthy young male medical students in Nepal whose findings suggest that there is no statistically significant relationship between smoking status and cognitive scores.

5. As observed in Table 5, for TMT-A scores, it is evident that none of the sociodemographic characteristics exhibit a significant correlation with TMT-A scores. This conclusion is supported by the large p-values associated with each of these variables, indicating a lack of statistically significant correlation with the TMT-A

scores. Therefore, based on the Pearson correlation analysis, there is no compelling evidence to suggest a significant relationship between TMT-A scores and the examined sociodemographic characteristics.

On the other hand, the TMT-B scores reveals that among the sociodemographic characteristics examined, only sex demonstrates a statistically significant and positive correlation with TMT-B scores, as indicated by a small p-value of 0.01. This implies that there exists a significant correlation between sex and TMT-B scores, suggesting that males, on average, exhibit higher TMT-B scores compared to females.

As sex being the only statistically significant correlation for TMT-B scores, this is consistent with a study conducted on university students in Egypt by Ibrahim, et. al. (2022), they reported that men were more significant users of tobacco (including smoking of cigarettes) and other substances such as alcohol than women. Their results also showed that the risk factors associated with drug use relate predominantly to gender and college type. In line with this, trends of tobacco-use observed by Pal (2019), stating that there were more male students who used tobacco compared to female students. Another study showing the same significance was from Gilbert, et. al. (2020). In their study, they stated that the use of e-cigarettes and poly-use of substances appeared higher in males as well as in adolescents who have lower grades. However, this does not mean that cigarette smoking has a direct effect on male performance in executive functioning and mental flexibility.

Conclusions

1. A total of 100 responses from the College of Criminology at the University of Caloocan City - Camarin Campus were gathered in which 50 of them were smokers and 50 were non-smokers. In the study, their demographic profile consists of a majority of 18-year-olds with more than half of the total sample being male (63%) and enrolled in the first year. Among smokers, the majority have been smoking for 5-6 years with an average consumption of more than 15 sticks per day.
2. There is enough statistical evidence to suggest that cigarette smoking has a significant effect on the visual attention and processing speed of young Filipino adults at the University of Caloocan City - Camarin Campus.
3. For TMT-A, the scores reflected a faster completion time in the non-smoker group which has been shown to be statistically significant. For TMT-B, a 0.1 statistical difference separates the scores of smokers and non-smokers with non-smokers being slightly higher, which is not statistically significant.
4. Lastly, based on the Pearson correlation analysis, there is no sufficient evidence to suggest that there is a significant relationship between the TMT-A scores and the sociodemographic characteristics of smokers and non-smokers. However, their TMT-B

scores imply that there is a significant correlation between sex and TMT-B scores, suggesting that males had a longer time to complete TMT-B which focuses not only on processing speed, but as well as executive function and mental flexibility. Although, this does not directly indicate that cigarette smoking is the only factor that affected their performance compared to females.

Recommendations

The investigation revealed that cigarette smoking significantly affects cognition, and males have a lower performance on executive functioning and mental flexibility. On this basis, public health campaigns and health education programs must also highlight the effects of smoking to cognitive function aside from potential diseases and well-known physical health risks of smoking. This may help the public grasp a better understanding on the dangers of smoking on the body and mind.

In the study of male and female smokers with regards to executive functioning similar to multitasking, it should be explored using a larger sample size, or a different population such as older adults. Longitudinal studies may be conducted to show the long-term effects of smoking to other cognitive domains. It is also recommended that future researchers consider other moderating variables (e.g., eating habits, sleep schedules, exercise or physical activity, and history of drug or alcohol abuse) that may strengthen or weaken the relationship between smoking and cognitive performance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors of this study hereby declare that all necessary ethical guidelines and protocols were strictly followed throughout the research process. The researchers have secured approval from their research adviser, the School of Respiratory Therapy, the Data Privacy Office, and the College of Criminology at the University of Caloocan - Camarin Campus to conduct the study. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, ensuring that they fully understood the nature and purpose of the study. Respondents were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences. Anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were maintained at all stages, ensuring that their personal information was protected as only the researchers of the study have access to the data gathered and will be destroyed after 5 weeks. The well-being of all respondents was prioritized and safeguarded throughout the research process.

Furthermore, the researchers affirm that there was no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study. The researchers strictly adhered to principles of academic integrity, avoiding any form of plagiarism. In addition, the researchers ensured that the data were analyzed and interpreted without bias, maintaining objectivity in all stages of the research. The findings and results of this study were used solely for

academic and research purposes, and any conclusions drawn were based purely on the data collected.

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